

DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS DURING THE ENGLISH STUDYING PROCESS

Xasanova Maftuna Sherali qizi

Toshkent davlat o‘zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti o‘qituvchisi

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Abstract. *This article is about the issues regarding the development of communicative competence of undergraduate students in the process of English learning during the practical classes. The article also reflects the methods and ways of formation of communicative skills, especially with the help of professional English games.*

Keywords: *communicative competence, methods and techniques of teaching, future teachers of English.*

International relations in business, industry, economy, and culture, which have increased in recent decades, place increased demands on modern specialists to communicate in foreign languages. In the process of modernization of education, there have been significant changes in the content of foreign language teaching. Communicative competence in its modern interpretation includes the following types of competencies: linguistic, sociolinguistic (speech), discursive, strategic, social, socio-cultural, subject, professional.

Communicativeness is the motivation of teaching; inclusion in communication; activity; interaction; meaningfulness; personal meaning; focus of exercises; communicative thinking; contrast; content; functionality; purposefulness; expressiveness; communicative value of phrases; pragmatics of speech; emotionality. Only compliance with all these characteristics allows us to call the educational process communicative.

Communicative competence is formed in all types of speech activity – listening and speaking, reading and writing, which ensures their implementation. Communicative competence is necessarily present in all four types of speech activity, ensuring the perception of speech works and their generation in the conditions of oral or written interaction of communication participants. In the junior years, we continue to develop students' basic communicative competencies. Students must achieve basic communicative competence in speaking, writing and listening, and advanced communicative competence in reading.

We know that communication-oriented English language teaching is possible in an activity-based approach. This approach is carried out through "activity tasks". They are implemented using methodological techniques and create exercises. To form communicative competence in the classroom, the teacher uses a variety of communicative exercises, which can be divided into 7 types: responsive, situational, reproductive, descriptive, debated, compositional, initiative.

Three types of exercises can be attributed to responsive exercises: question-and-answer, replica, conditional conversation.

Question-and-answer exercises are considered the most popular in the methodology of teaching oral foreign language speech. With the help of questions, the teacher can train certain structures, vocabulary, and check how students understood the text.

From the replica exercises, the following are used: statement- question (the response expresses surprise, doubt, re-questioning, clarification, assumption, etc.); statement - statement (the response expresses agreement, amendment, promise); statement - denial (the response

expresses disagreement, objection, protest). Examples of such exercises can be: reading small dialogues and drawing up a diagram of the speech clichés used; expressing agreement with these statements or refuting them; expressing surprise with a question, etc.

A conditional conversation should become a free conversation (requesting information about a person of interest, an object, an event; informing; expressing one's attitude; exchanging opinions and impressions; establishing contact; supporting the conversation).

Situational exercises are associated with problematic, imaginary, role-playing situations. Any educational and speech situation is a micro theme of oral speech (for example, tell me what you would do in this situation; solve the problem; act as a role, etc.).

The category of reproductive exercises includes retelling, retelling-translation, abbreviated selective presentation, dramatization. These exercises have all the features of a really motivated speech action and are very appropriate in foreign language lessons.

In the undergraduate courses, debating exercises (educational discussion, commenting) are used. Students are offered the following topics for discussion: "How do teenagers spend their holidays in Britain", "Problems of teenagers", "An unforgettable gift", "Who is a real hero?", "What do you use a mobile phone for?", "A good hotel. What is it like?". Commenting as an exercise is designed to develop students' monologue (for example, to comment on a TV program; an announcement; a humorous drawing of a newspaper article, etc.).

An important pedagogical condition for the formation of students' communicative competencies is the teacher's use of innovative learning technologies. The modern educational process of teaching a foreign language cannot be imagined without project technology.

The project form of work allows students to apply their accumulated knowledge on the subject. Students expand their horizons, the boundaries of language proficiency, gaining experience from its practical use, learn to listen to foreign language speech and hear and understand each other when defending projects. The guys work with reference literature, dictionaries, and a computer, thereby creating the possibility of direct contact with an authentic language, which is not provided by learning a language only with the help of a textbook in the classroom. In the process of working on the project, all four types of speech activity should be present – speaking, reading, writing, listening – in an integrated form. In addition, the development of language skills occurs when there is a need for them in the process of working on a project. For example, speaking and listening are used in interviews or social surveys, writing is used while recording information received from a partner, reading is used when extracting information necessary for the implementation of a project from brochures, booklets, etc.

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